

THE PROBLEM OF DEPRECIATION OF NATIONAL VALUES

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Annotation. The article presents the problems of depreciation of the national age and its socio-philosophical analysis. The question of the occurrence of national value in crisis in modern society and its impact on social stability has been studied.

Key words: National value, value, spiritual values, political values, natural values, universal values, ethics, consciousness, rights and duty.

In the new century, the acceleration and complication of social and economic, international political and cultural ties on the world arena made social stability a central factor in ensuring progress and prosperity. In fact, let's say that in order to accelerate the pace of economic development, attract investments in the country's economy, create new jobs, raise the standard of living of the population, it is primarily necessary to ensure social stability. Without it, it is impossible to strengthen the foundations of a democratic society and ensure the optimal functioning of civil society institutions. Ultimately, it will also be necessary to strengthen social stability in order to develop culture, art and science, preserve cultural heritage, develop the creative potential of citizens. On the basis of these considerations, it can be noted that by the 21st century, the issue of maintaining and strengthening social stability has become a strategic task of any modern society.

So, while the socio-economic, political and cultural prosperity of the country dictates the strengthening of social stability, what should be done to ensure it? Experts in response to this question mention its many economic, social, political, legal, cultural factors. It is therefore necessary to point out that social stability also requires the exaltation of spiritual values. Because it is spiritual values that serve to strengthen the factors of social stability. This can be expressed as:

First. Social stability is ensured through a Democratic political system. Spiritual values, on the other hand, are the main factor that gives rise to a Democratic political system.

It is known that the Democratic political system is a form of government based on the principles of democracy, in which the people will be able to

participate in political decision-making, control power through elections and democratic institutions. Its main categories of characteristics include the distribution of power, the existence of free and fair elections, the rule of law, the guarantee of human rights, the provision of freedom of speech, etc . The Democratic political system plays an important role in deciding social stability. In particular, it serves to increase the Social Responsibility and activity of members of society while giving citizens the opportunity to participate in the process of making political decisions through various social mechanisms. The governing mechanisms of the Democratic political system do not allow the abuse of power, prevent corruption and, therefore, ensure the rule of law. While it creates pluralism of views, it sets the stage for resolving social disagreements with Humane styles and strengthening social harmony. The guarantee of human rights and freedoms in the context of a Democratic political system also contributes to the formation of civil society and the decision-making of social stability.

Spiritual values are precisely the factor of the formation of a political system that serves to ensure such social stability. Because they create the attitude of people to state institutions, socio-political mechanisms, socio-political processes in order to influence the beliefs, qualities, Life Principles of members of society. Spiritual values such as peace, freedom, civil rights and duties, social discipline, social justice contribute to the formation of a democratic culture. It is possible to make laws recognizing democratic norms and principles in society, apply social mechanisms that implement it, financially secure the activities of institutions that serve democracy – but at the same time, since spiritual values are not elevated in society, these elements do not merge into a holistic Democratic political system and do not serve social stability.

Ikinchidan. Yuzaga keladi restoration of stability of human life, erkinliklari and zhamiyatdaging's yakukuklari. This verse says that the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) was one of the companions of the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him).

Human rights and the sustainable rights of society are absolute rights that are valued by all, and they are guaranteed by the State. In accordance with the country's Constitution and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Bundestag highly values and resolutely protects human rights and the Erkinklar. Every member of the society has the right to membership and legal status. Human rights and sustainable development are an important resource for rebuilding a social community. As the Bundesliga sought to seize power in

Uzbekistan, it was possible at certain times to mobilize political resources around the world.

In order for the priority Society of human rights and freedoms to decide, the existing laws must be permeated with humanistic and democratic norms and principles, of course. But there is only one side to this issue. Therefore, in society, the corresponding spiritual values are also developed darcor. Spiritual values play an important role in the formation of a society in which human rights and freedoms are prioritized, as they lay the groundwork for justice, equality, human dignity, kindness, visions of tolerance and dreams to take place from the structure of laws. In other words, when spiritual values such as justice, equality, human dignity, kindness, tolerance are glorified in society, these values will sooner or later be expressed in the system of laws of society. Thanks to spiritual values, an idea is formed in the members of society that human rights should be strictly guaranteed, and peat relations between people should correspond to the norms of law and law. This vision is the basis of the decision-making of a society in which human rights and freedoms are prioritized.

In a society where spiritual values such as justice, equality, human dignity, kindness, tolerance are not deeply rooted, people cannot use the rights and freedoms recognized by law, do not respect the rights of others. Naturally, such a society will be invaluable from social harmony and stability.

Thirdly. Social stability is a product of a healthy moral environment. Spiritual values, on the other hand, serve as a factor that shapes the moral environment.

Moral environment refers to the moral conditions that arise in society on the basis of certain moral knowledge and values, norms and norms. A number of these conditions arise in contrast to the activities of interrelated institutions. For example, the basis of the moral environment is family values, traditions and lifestyle, since it is the family that forms the initial perceptions of morality. The educational system plays an important role in the formation of the moral environment, the transmission of universally recognized moral values, norms and norms to young people. Media and cultural and educational institutions provide a translation of moral values. The role of religious factors in the formation of the moral environment of society is also great . As the activities of these institutions become rational and proportional to social interests, the moral environment of society also becomes healthier. In such an environment, people begin to diligently fulfill their social duties, get used to respect the worldview and beliefs, rights and freedoms of members of other societies, become

something to sympathize with others. A healthy moral environment creates conditions of mutual trust and constructive communication in society. It is for this reason that the moral environment can be recognized as one of the important bases of social stability. The erosion of this base makes society fit from stability, leads to recession. In general, looking at the experience of history, we see that at all times the instability and degradation of all societies began precisely with the unhealthy nature of the moral environment.

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